

Software Workshop Participant Survey

1. Email *

2. Did you establish new collaborations around software for the NASA Science Mission Directorate?

Mark only one oval.

Many

Some

None

3. If you did establish new collaborations, what types of collaboration are they (check all that apply).

Check all that apply.

Same center

Different center

Same discipline

Different discipline

Not applicable

4. Do you have a greater understanding of NASA software policies and practices?

Mark only one oval.

- Much greater understanding
- Somewhat greater understanding
- About the same
- Less understanding

5. Do you have a greater understanding of resources available to aid software development and release?

Mark only one oval.

- Much greater understanding
- Somewhat greater understanding
- About the same
- Less understanding

6. Did you discover new software that you are considering incorporating into your work?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

7. Did you get at least one new idea for software improvements or development that you could implement?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

8. Do you think NASA gained a better understanding of community issues around software and will be able to prioritize a way forward?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Maybe

9. Should we continue workshops like these?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, annually
- Yes, periodically as needed
- No
- Not sure

10. What suggestions do you have for improving how the meeting is organized?

11. What suggestions do you have to foster greater software collaboration across SMD?

12. What topics would you like to see addressed at future workshops?

13. Any other suggestions, kudos, ideas, proposals?

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

